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RESHAPING THE ISLAMIC FINANCE INDUSTRY APPLYING THE LESSONS LEARNT FROM THE GLOBAL FINANCIAL CRISIS

Rafe Haneef

Research Fellow

International Shari'ah Research Academy for Islamic Finance (ISRA)

Edib Smolo

Researcher

International Shari'ah Research Academy for Islamic Finance (ISRA)

Reshaping the Islamic Finance Industry

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Rafe Haneef and Edib Smolo

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In the last 27 years, the world has witnessed more than 124 distinct financial crises. The financial meltdown caused by the current global financial crisis brought the financial world to its knees. Due to its severity, it has been labeled the worst crisis since the Great Depression (for example see Jones, 2009; Nonomiya & Lanman, 2008; NY Times, 2010, January 12; Volcker, 2010). It is now, more than ever before, clear that the current financial system is not flawless. The severity of the recent asset-bubble burst has raised questions about the merits of *laissez-faire* capitalism and the theory of a rational market as highlighted in the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH). There has been growing interest in the work of Hyman Minsky and his ‘financial instability hypothesis’ (Minsky, 2008) following the American sub-prime mortgage crisis. According to this hypothesis, the accumulation of debt is the initial trigger for financial crisis. Economic stability in the short-run breeds instability in the long-run as debt accumulates to unsustainable levels.

Notably, the prolonged period of ‘moderation’ following previous crises, such as the 2001 dot-com bubble, together with what is termed as ‘the Global Saving Glut’, paved the way for the current crisis. In addition, easy money, uncontrolled growth of

* Rafe Haneef is a Managing Director at Fajr Capital Limited, an Islamic investment holding company. He is also currently a Research Fellow of International Shari’ah Research Academy for Islamic Finance (ISRA). He can be contacted at rafe.haneef@fajrcapital.com.

** Edib Smolo is a researcher at International Shari’ah Research Academy for Islamic Finance (ISRA). He can be contacted at edib@isra.my.

credit and debts, lax regulation and supervision, innovation of complex financial structures that far exceeded the real potential and needs of the economy, mismanagement of risks involved, lack of disclosure and transparency, predatory lending and high leveraging—among other factors—can be traced as the main culprits of the crisis. The distinguishing feature of the current financial crisis is that it originated in a developed economy, that of the United States of America, as compared to the other crises of the last half-century (Truman, 2009).

The global financial crisis also brought the Islamic financial industry (IFI) into the limelight as a possible and viable alternative. Its underlying principles, deeply rooted in the teachings of the Sharī‘ah (Islamic law), proved to be a blessing for the IFI. The crisis had a limited impact on Islamic finance, although it did not emerge totally unscathed. At the same time, the crisis provided a necessary shock for Islamic finance to evaluate its own practices and position within the global financial architecture. Such an evaluation of current practices has to be performed from an ethico-legal perspective to ensure that the industry is not replicating the conventional path but adhering to the spirit of what the Sharī‘ah intended in financial contracts.

In short, the global financial crisis offers both a challenge and opportunity for Islamic finance. How Muslim scholars will respond to these challenges will clearly define the future of Islamic finance. As Karuvelil stated (2000, p. 155): “The [Islamic finance] industry faces considerable challenges; its response to them will determine whether it becomes a significant alternative to the conventional system in global financial markets.”

This paper consists of five sections, including the introduction. The second section highlights the main lessons from the financial crisis. As identifying the lessons from the crisis is only one part of the story, the redressing of issues and flaws in the current financial architecture is the focus of Section Three. Section Four focuses on reshaping the behaviors of the economic agents. Special focus is given to Islamic finance and the importance of ethico-legal principles necessary for building a healthier and more stable financial system.

2.0 LESSONS LEARNT FROM THE CURRENT GLOBAL CRISIS

The inherent features of the recent crisis, which commentators consider unique among other international financial crises of recent decades, provide a backdrop for framing an evaluation of the current financial architecture. Firstly, the recent financial crisis originated in the United States—a seemingly highly developed financial and legal system—as compared to other past crises, which began in emerging markets. Secondly, the fact that a U.S. subprime mortgage crisis evolved into a global financial crisis should not surprise us since the currency and the institutions of the United States are at the core of the global financial system. And thirdly, this recent crisis began in the financial sector and then moved to the real economy, creating a feedback cycle that further weakened the financial sector and real economy (Truman, 2009a).

Upon a review of the available literature on the current global financial crisis, it appears that there is no consensus on the causes of the current financial crisis. Some argue that the complexity and intensive use of structured financial products, derivatives and other assets with uncertain fundamentals played a key role in triggering the crisis (Aziz, 2008; FSF, 2008; Jordan & Jain, 2009, October; Mersch, 2009, p. 14; Mirakhor & Krichene, 2009; Mizen, 2008; NY Times, 2010, January 12; Sarkar, 2009, September; Truman, 2009a, 2009b; Yellen, 2009, May). Other commentators note a combination of loose monetary policy, lax financial supervision and a trend towards deregulation, (Aziz, 2008; Cooper, 2008, p. 171; Kashyap, Rajan, & Stein, 2008; Taylor, 2008, November; Truman, 2009a, 2009b), together with low interest rates, excessive leveraging and credit growth as the fundamental factors that ignited the crisis (Aziz, 2008; Bordo, 2008; Mirakhor & Krichene, 2009; OECD, 2009a, 2009b; Roubini, 2008; Truman, 2009a). This view has been endorsed in the World Economic Forum's Financial Development Report 2008:

These crises [currency crises, sovereign debt crises, systemic banking or financial crises, systemic corporate crises, systemic household debt crises] are often preceded by asset bubbles and the credit bubbles that feed them... However, many asset bubbles have been associated with episodes of easy monetary policy and excessive credit growth.

The perverse interaction between easy money, asset bubbles, credit growth, and leveraging that feed asset bubbles has been observed in many episodes. The initial trigger for a bubble may (but not necessarily) be a period of easy money with relatively low real interest rates. Such a low cost of capital and easy liquidity may lead to an initial increase in the asset price above its fundamental value. Since asset purchases are often financed by credit, the initial increase in the asset prices allows borrowers to borrow more as the asset price rise increases the value of collateral that can be used to increase leverage. With higher asset prices, the collateral value of borrowing to finance further asset purchases is higher, with increased leverage allowing additional asset purchases that further increases the collateral that then allows further borrowing and leveraging, entering into a vicious circle... Thus, easy money and easy credit may be an initial trigger of a process of asset bubbles and excessive leveraging of the financial system and of the private non-financial sector (Roubini, 2008, pp. 34-35).

The events of the last couple of years have revealed failures on two fronts: one of them is the failure of the risk management practices used by the private sector, and the other is the failure of the public sector's oversight of the financial system (Aziz, 2008; Bernanke, 2009). Among other things, Federal Reserve Chairman Ben S. Bernanke concludes that "capital adequacy, effective liquidity planning, and strong risk management are essential for safe and sound banking; the crisis revealed serious deficiencies on the part of some financial institutions in one or more of the areas" (Bernanke, 2009). In other words, failure of one or more of these core elements of safe and sound banking would lead to a crisis. This is exactly what happened prior to the recent financial crisis.

One of the important lessons that emerged in the wake of the current financial crisis is the effect of globalization. The globalization of trade, finance, capital and labor has tied together countries all over the world. Countries are now more interlinked and interdependent than ever before. Modern technology has expedited the transfer of information instantaneously, for better or for worse. Consequently, any panic or any crisis that affects a major interlinked economy or a group of countries has the ability to spread to other countries—the "contagion effect" (Aziz, 2008; Jones, 2009; Jordan & Jain, 2009, October; Kashyap, et al., 2008; Truman, 2009a; Yellen, 2009, May).

Aside from the abovementioned lessons, we would like to summarize here the major lessons that are common to all the cited authors.

2.1 Risk Transfers and Imprudent Credit Growth

The current financial turmoil is a direct result of an exceptional boom in credit growth and leverage within the financial system (Aziz, 2008; Financial Stability Forum, 2008, p. 1 & 5). A low-interest-rate regime that lasted for too long and lax lending standards contributed to the current crisis (Bordo, 2008; Jones, 2009; Mizen, 2008; Nonomiya & Lanman, 2008; NY Times, 2010, January 12). The low interest rate lured both borrowers to borrow more than they could handle and financial institutions to devise new products and grant excessively risky loans in search of high profits in a low interest-rate environment (Mizen, 2008).

This is not surprising, as conventional banking in particular and the financial industry in general is based on interest-based debt intermediation supported by deposit insurance schemes under the canopy of a lender of last resort. One of the main sources of income for conventional financial institutions is the interest charged on loans granted by banks to customers. More precisely, banks make their profit from the spread between the interest paid on deposits and the interest earned on loans. Given that banks will face losses if they are unable to recover their loans with interest, they are expected to carefully analyze each and every loan application so as to minimize the risk of loss.

However, banks driven by shareholder interest and the desire for profit-maximization started to indulge in excessive and imprudent lending. Over the long period of a low-interest-rate regime, lenders were extending loans to borrowers who borrowed more than they could afford (Jordan & Jain, 2009, October). According to the Bank for International Settlements (BIS), the fundamental cause for the current global financial crisis lies in “excessive and imprudent credit growth over a long period” (BIS, 2008, p. 143). Lionel Robbins once remarked that “the pursuit of self-interest, unrestrained by suitable institutions, carries no guarantee of anything but chaos” (Robbins, 1952 as

cited in Mirakhor & Krichene, 2009, p. 71). Furthermore, depositors were oblivious to the excessive risk-taking appetite of the banks, given that their deposits are either expressly guaranteed by deposit insurance schemes or implicitly guaranteed by the lender of last resort, the central banks.

Nevertheless, banks alone should not be blamed for the current global crisis, as they were merely playing by the “rules of the game” that governments have established in financial markets. If deposits were not guaranteed, expressly or implicitly, by the government, and if bank managers were to be made personally liable for their irrational and irresponsible decisions, they would obviously be more cautious in their lending decisions. There are, therefore, three factors that influence and explain the banks’ imprudent lending practices: The first factor is the banks’ ability to freely transfer their risk to third parties by selling their loan portfolios. In the past when risk transfers were not prevalent, banks used to be more prudent in their lending practices, given that they would have to “hold-to-maturity” their loan portfolios. When banks know that they can transfer their risks by way of securitization, collateralized debt obligations and other risk-transfer mechanisms, they are incentivized to assume excessive risks in pursuit of greater profits.

The second factor is the sense of security that both banks as well as depositors acquire from the “too big to fail” syndrome, whereby, in case of a crisis, the central bank would assume the responsibility to bail out the bank in order to contain a systemic risk to the economy. Many commentators firmly believe that it is due to this reason that banks ended up taking greater risks than they would have otherwise undertaken independently (Chapra, 2008; Mishkin, 1997, pp. 61-62).

The third factor is again related to the guarantee mechanism in the current financial framework: the deposit insurance companies that guarantee citizens’ deposits. In the absence of such deposit insurance, banks would need to be more careful when investing depositor money, and at the same time depositors would be more cautious when choosing their banks (see Roubini, 2008, p. 41).

This leads us to the next lesson, which is the failure of risk management procedures by the major financial institutions.

2.2 Failure of Risk Management

As mentioned above by Bernanke (2009), risk management is paramount for safe and sound banking. Rapid financial innovation and product development, which seemed to have reached their pinnacle in the last decade, made risk management extremely challenging. While financial innovation brings improvements and benefits to market participants, problems arise if new products bring with them unnecessary complications resulting in new risks that are less understood, assessed and controlled. As a result, the inadequacy of risk management practices of many financial institutions was exposed (Ahmed, 2009; Aziz, 2008; Bernanke, 2009; FSF, 2008, p. 7; Mirakhor & Krichene, 2009; Trichet, 2009). The Financial Stability Forum concluded that “[t]he market turmoil has revealed weaknesses in risk management at the banks and securities firms at the core of the global financial system, and in the system of incentives that regulators and supervisors provide through capital and liquidity requirements and oversight” (FSF, 2008, p. 12).

The increased complexity of financial products and markets deteriorated the ability of market participants, regulators and supervisors to evaluate the risks. In other words, the risks inherent in these new products were mispriced (see Mizen, 2008, p. 554; Taylor, 2008, November). Consequently, risk management practices have to be regularly updated to reflect the changes in instruments, markets and business models. Regulators and supervisors should also make sure that financial institutions do not engage in activities without having adequate skills and controls (FSF, 2008).

This crisis revealed the importance of maintaining effective risk management practices. As Bernanke noted, “It is precisely during those good times, when risks appear low and the financial horizon seems clear, that financial market participants can become overly optimistic and make costly mistakes” (Bernanke, 2009).

2.3 Liquidity and Leveraging

Risk-taking, from an Islamic finance point of view, is considered not only good but also necessary, based on the well known legal maxim ‘*Al-kharāj bi al-ḍamān*,’ i.e., entitlement to profit or gain depends on the corresponding liability for loss. However, exposing oneself or one’s wealth to unnecessary or excessive risk is seen as gambling (*maysir*), and such risk-taking is prohibited.

The European Central Bank defines liquidity as “the ease and speed with which a financial asset can be converted into cash or used to settle a liability. Cash is thus a highly liquid asset. The term ‘liquidity’ is also often used as a synonym for money” (European Central Bank (ECB), 2010). The current crisis revealed the importance of liquidity and liquidity risk management for efficient functioning of financial markets (Allen & Carletti, 2008; Aziz, 2008; Bernanke, 2009; Bordo, 2008; Mersch, 2009, p. 10; OECD, 2009a). It is believed that one of the triggers of the crisis was the excessive liquidity of financial institutions, a result of their search for high yield and extra profits (Mirakhor & Krichene, 2009). Liquidity risk management is important due to its role in maintaining institutional and systemic resilience in the face of shocks. Liquidity shortfall of even one institution can cause system-wide repercussions (Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, 2008, p. 1; FSF, 2008, p. 16).

Since the crisis, the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS) has published a number of papers and principles on the issue, including: “*Principles for Sound Liquidity Risk Management and Supervision*”, “*Sound Practices for Managing Liquidity in Banking Organisations*” and “*Liquidity Risk Management and Supervisory Challenges*”. The studies showed the failure of many banks to take into account very basic principles of liquidity risk management when liquidity was plentiful. (For details, see Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, 2008, pp. 3-5.)

2.4 Lax Regulation and Supervision

According to Warren and Tyagi (February, 2009), although many economists and financial experts have given different reasons for the current financial meltdown, they all failed to identify the major culprit: the weak “legal structure governing the sale of mortgages, credit cards, and other consumer financial products” (p. 22).

Many experts, time and again, have highlighted the importance of the regulatory and supervisory framework for the smooth functioning of a stable system. Supervision and regulation of the financial sector, or rather the lack of both, played a role in the crisis (Bordo, 2008; Truman, 2009b). The limited scope of the regulatory framework allowed the growth of unregulated exposures, which led to excessive risk-taking and weak liquidity risk management (Aziz, 2008; FSF, 2008, p. 9).

It is now clear that the regulatory and supervisory frameworks of many countries in general, and the United States in particular, were incomplete and inefficient (Jordan & Jain, 2009, October). Over the years, the so-called ‘shadow financial system’—consisting of money market mutual funds, special purpose investment vehicles, hedge funds, private equity firms, among other vehicles and players—developed. As these institutions were less regulated, the traditional banks were motivated to shift to their use in pursuit of profit maximization. In order to compete with these less-regulated institutions, traditional banks developed new models which led to the overleveraging of the global financial system, especially in the United States. Once the good days waned, the artificial financial system collapsed (Truman, 2009a).

Lax regulation and supervision led to extensive innovation, which far exceeded the real potential and needs of the economy. As result, the financial crisis was an inevitable reality. It is true that lax regulations leave more space for the development of the financial system and that over-regulation may harm it, but it is also true that if a proper regulatory framework had been in place the effects of the financial crisis could have been less devastating. In other words, as Mirakhor and Krichene (2009) stated, we need “‘efficient’, rather than ‘more’, regulations and supervision that avoids

excesses in risk-taking” (p. 33).¹ Therefore, what we need is a prudent and up-to-date regulatory and supervisory framework that will be able cope with the ever-increasing needs of the financial market (Nier, 2009, April). We need to find a golden mean that will be equally applicable in good times and bad.

2.5 Transparency and Disclosure

Another lesson that can be drawn from the current turmoil is the issue of transparency and disclosure. It is inextricably related to all the previously highlighted lessons. The innovation that brought about new products with new, less understandable risks and exposures, combined with opaque disclosure of information by the financial system, led market players astray and played a decisive role in underestimation of the risks involved. The low level of transparency and disclosure that accompanied all the other factors damaged market confidence and contributed to panic in the market (see Aziz, 2008; OECD, 2009a, p. 36).

All of the above point to one conclusion: that reliable valuation together with effective and usable disclosure of the risks associated with new products (especially structured credit products) are very important for a sound financial system. The Financial Stability Forum (FSF) concludes that “sound disclosure, accounting and valuation practices are essential to achieve transparency, to maintain market confidence and to promote effective market discipline” (FSF, 2008, p. 22).

2.6 Debt- and Interest-Based Financing

Muslim scholars and economists, as well as many Western economists and financial think-tanks, argue that the prevailing debt-based financial system and its financial instruments are among the causes (if not the main cause) of the current global financial crisis.

¹ The italics here are ours, added for emphasis.

The interest-based financial system inevitably helps the rich to get richer while keeping the poor mired in poverty or driving them deeper into it. As Dusuki (2009) pointed out, over-emphasis on debt-based instruments in the economy would not help to remove the injustices, harm, inequity and inefficiency that are inimical to the objectives of the Sharī'ah. It is due to the interest-based system that we have the unjust and uneven distribution of wealth that damages the interests of common people. This has been criticized even by Western economists such as James Robertson. He says:

The pervasive role of interest in the economic system results in the systematic transfer of money from those who have less to those who have more. Again, this transfer of resources from poor to rich has been made shockingly clear by the Third World debt crisis. But it applies universally. It is partly because those who have more money to lend, get more in interest than those who have less; it is partly because those who have less, often have to borrow more; and it is partly because the cost of interest repayments now forms a substantial element in the cost of all goods and services, and the necessary goods and services loom much larger in the finances of the rich. When we look at the money system that way and when we begin to think about how it should be redesigned to carry out its functions fairly and efficiently as part of an enabling and conserving economy, the arguments for an interest-free, inflation-free money system for the twenty-first century seem to be very strong. (Robertson, 1990, pp. 130-131; as cited in Usmani, 2010a)

The following citation summarizes the previous discussion:

[T]he conventional view holds that the emergence of the crisis was due to a number of factors, including: extraordinarily high liquidity; rapid pace of financial engineering which innovated complex, opaque and difficult-to-understand financial instruments way ahead of the market; informational problems caused by lack of transparency in asset market prices, particularly in the market for structured credit instruments; outdated, lax or absent regulatory-supervisory oversight, which encouraged excessive risk-taking; faulty risk management and accounting models; and the emergence of an incentive structure that created a complicit coalition composed of financial institutions, real estate developers and appraisers, insurance companies and credit-rating agencies whose actions led to a deliberate underestimation and underpricing of risk (Mirakhor & Krichene, 2009, p. 33).

3.0 REDRESSING THE CURRENT FINANCIAL ARCHITECTURE

Identifying the lessons from the current global financial crisis is one side of the coin, while the other side is implementing practicable measures to avoid the past mistakes. As Bernanke repeatedly asked (2008a, 2008b, 2009): *What have we learned from this extraordinary episode? And how can we apply those lessons to strengthen our banking system and avoid or mitigate future crises?*

From an Islamic finance perspective, Mirakhor and Krichene (2009) concluded that “the most important lesson of the recent crisis for Islamic finance is an urgent need for the design, development and implementation of a comprehensive, unified, uniform, global and dynamic regulatory-prudential-supervisory framework” (p. 71). This “properly designed regulatory-prudential-supervisory framework,” the authors further argued, is “essential to the orderly development and evolution of Islamic finance” (pp. 68-69).

3.1 Shift towards Equity-Based Financing

Shaykh Muhammad Taqi Usmani, in his address to the recent World Economic Forum in Davos, called for restructuring the international financial system in general and Islamic finance in particular. He proposed that the current debt-based system be replaced with an equity-based system that is more linked to the real economy. As mentioned earlier, there is a role for debt in every financial system (be it Islamic or otherwise), but it should not be predominant. In other words, the use of debt should be a last resort approach, once all other options are exhausted (Usmani, 2010a, 2010b). Shaykh Taqi’s recommendation has been supported by many Muslim scholars and economists.

However, debt-oriented financing has to be viewed in the context of a financial system based on a fractional reserve banking model. Debt financing has been accorded significant pricing advantages in the current financial system. Islamic finance cannot refrain from debt-based financing unless the government is prepared to

replace the existing fractional reserve banking model with an entirely Shari'ah-based model. Until such time when a Shari'ah-based financial system is implemented, Islamic financiers must ensure that the scope of Islamic debt financing is limited for constructive and essential purposes only. Debt financing should not be extended for irrational and wasteful consumption or speculation. Islam has clearly laid down certain conditions to help prevent excessive expansion of debt. Some of these conditions are mentioned by Chapra (2008, pp. 15-16) as follows:

1. The asset which is being sold or leased must be *real*, and not imaginary or notional;
2. The seller must own and possess the goods being sold or leased;
3. The transaction must be a genuine trade transaction with full intention of giving and taking delivery; and
4. The debt cannot be sold, and thus, the risk associated with it cannot be transferred to someone else. It must be borne by the creditor himself.

In order to prevent the recurrence of crises in the future, according to Chapra (2008, p. 2), we need the combination of three forces, namely:

1. Establishing moral constraints on greed for maximum profits, wealth, and consumption;
2. The need for market discipline that will exercise a restraint on leverage, excessive lending and derivatives.
3. Reform of the system's structure, combined with prudential regulation and supervision, to prevent crises, achieve sustainable development and protect social interests.

4.0 RESHAPING THE BEHAVIOR AND RESPONSIBILITIES OF ECONOMIC AGENTS

As already mentioned, debt-based financing has a limited role in Islam. To understand the scope of debt in Islam, and its subsequent impact on the behavior and

responsibilities of economic agents in an Islamic financial system, we need to look into the primary sources of the Sharī‘ah: the Qur’ān and Ḥadīth.

The longest verse in the Holy Qur’ān is *Āyat al-Dayn* or the Verse on Debt (verse 282, Sūrah al-Baqarah). From the layman’s perspective, the length of this *ayah* is in itself an indication of its importance. Allah SWT says in this verse: “O you who believe! When you contract a debt for a fixed period, write it down...”

Abū Ja‘far al-Ṭabarī said that whenever there is a transaction involving debt for a specified period (whether it is created through sale or loan), it should be written down (Al-Tabari, 2000/1420, p. 43). In short, this *āyah* lays down the foundation and fundamental principles when drafting the debt contract. Some of these principles are briefly mentioned here: First, it is obvious that the debt contract should be written down; second, the time period should be known and specified; third, the person writing down the contract (*kātib*) should be just and trustworthy; fourth, the *kātib* has to treat both seller (creditor) and buyer (debtor) fairly and not be biased toward either one of them. (for full list of principles see Al-Sa’adi, 2000/1420, p. 118).

‘Ā’ishah (may Allah be pleased with her) reported that the Prophet (peace be upon him) would frequently say in his prayers: “*O Allah, I seek refuge with You from the trial of the grave and from the trial of Masīh al-Dajjāl and from the afflictions of life and death. O Allah, I seek refuge with you from sins (ma’tam) and from being in debt (maghram).*” When asked, “*Why do you so frequently seek refuge with Allah from being in debt?*” the Prophet (peace be upon him) replied, “*A person in debt tells lies whenever he speaks and breaks promises whenever he makes (them)*” (Al-Bukhari, 1987/1407a, p. 286, hadith no. 798; Al-Bayhaqi, 1994b, p. 453).

In another *ḥadīth* narrated by Abu Sa‘īd (may Allah be pleased with him), the Prophet (peace be upon him) was once seeking protection from *kufir* (disbelief) and *dayn* (debt); a man asked him, “Is *dayn* on a par with *kufir*?” The Prophet (peace be upon him) replied, “Yes” (see Al-Nasa’i, 1420, p. 658). The Prophet (peace be upon him)

also declined to perform funeral prayers for a companion who died with an outstanding debt.²

There appears to be only one instance in which the Prophet (peace be upon him) borrowed for his personal interest, and that was to buy food, which is an essential need. ‘Ā’ishah (may Allah be pleased with her) reported that the Holy Prophet (peace be upon him) bought food on credit from a Jew, for which he pledged his new armor (Al-Bukhari, 1987/1407b, p. 887). The other instances in which the Prophet (peace be upon him) borrowed, he did so to help the poor and needy. In all these reports it is evidently clear that the Prophet (peace be upon him) only took debt for essential requirements and that he constantly sought Allah’s protection from debt.

Given the limited scope of credit (debt) in the Sharī‘ah, the bank (as seller) should be transparent, responsible and accountable for the credit facilities offered to the market. Similarly, the customers who seek credit must also be responsible and ensure that they do not resort to debt impulsively or capriciously. In addition, regulators have a responsibility to ensure that both sellers (banks) and buyers (customers) conform to these standards. The questions, therefore, that need to be addressed here are: How do we reshape the regulatory framework for the financial system to ensure compliance with these Sharī‘ah standards? The authors firmly believe that the standard of care imposed by the Sharī‘ah on both the providers and seekers of credit is considerably higher than the standards prevailing in other jurisdictions, which are based on the principles of either *caveat venditor* (let the seller beware) or *caveat emptor* (let the buyer beware). The standard of care in the Sharī‘ah is based on ethico-legal principles which link ethical considerations to legal requirements. The following illustrations may help to better explain the Islamic perspective on ethico-legal requirements.

Conventional banks skillfully deploy various marketing tactics to lure customers to seek loans and other debt financing from the bank. It is not uncommon for

² In an authentic *hadith* on the issue, Salamah ibn al-Akwa‘ related that a deceased man was brought to the Prophet (peace be upon him), who asked, “Is there any debt on him?” [The companions] replied, “Yes.” He asked, “Has he left anything [behind to repay the debt]?” They replied, “No.” He said, “Pray on your companion.” Abū Qatādah said: “O Messenger of Allah, [the debt] is on me.” Then only did the Prophet (peace be upon him) pray on the deceased (Al-Bayhaqi, 1994c, p. 73; n.d., p. 96).

conventional banks to slash their personal loan rates—for example, during festival seasons—to entice their customers to borrow and spend beyond their means in order to satisfy their impulsive desires while in a festive mood. Such marketing tactics are clearly within the boundaries of legal permissibility; however, they may not conform to Islamic ethico-legal principles. For example, one can observe Islamic banks slashing their personal finance rate during Ramaḍān to entice customers to borrow beyond their means. Isn't Ramaḍān the month for *'ibādah* and other good deeds? Should Islamic banks skillfully deploy shrewd marketing tactics to entice customers into debt as conventional banks do? Legally, Islamic banks may be entitled to slash the rates whenever they like, but from an Islamic ethico-legal perspective, should Islamic banks 'entrap' customers by skillfully playing upon their impulsive desires?

Unfortunately, the current offering of Sharī'ah-compliant products is focused only on the *ḥalāl* or legal aspects of the transactions, without taking into consideration the ethical dimensions that Islam purposes to achieve. Islamic banks are under a duty of care to educate the customers that, although debt is *ḥalāl*, it should not be simply resorted to in accordance with one's whims and fancies. Like *ṭalāq* (divorce), debt should be resorted to only when there is a genuine necessity and upon due care and consideration. *Ṭalāq*, like debt, is also *ḥalāl*, but is the most detestable among the things made permissible by Allah SWT.³ In this context, the authors firmly believe that debt should be treated similar to *ṭalāq* (divorce) and resorted to only as a last option.

If debt is comparable to *ṭalāq* in terms of scope of permissibility in Islam, should Islamic banks indulge in clever marketing tactics to entice customers to debt? We can't imagine the Sharī'ah allowing, for example, divorce lawyers to deploy artful marketing tactics to solicit their legal services for *ṭalāq* at a discounted fee to lure

³ Ibn 'Umar (may Allah be pleased with him and his father) narrated that the Prophet (peace be upon him) said: "*The most detestable ḥalāl (lawful thing) to Allah is ṭalāq (divorce)*" (al-Bayhaqī, (1994a, p. 322, hadith no. 14671). This *ḥadīth* was also reported by Abū Dāwūd (2/255, no. 2178); Ibn Mājah (1/650, no. 2018); al-Ḥākim (2/214, no. 2794), who stated that its chain of narrators (*sanad*) is *ṣaḥīḥ*; Ibn 'Adī (6/461), and al-Ṭabarānī.

‘disgruntled’ spouses into divorce! Surely, from an ethico-legal perspective the lawyers must advise the clients that they should try to make the marriage work, given that *ṭalāq* should only be resorted to as a final option in the Sharī‘ah. Should Islamic bankers also be required from an Islamic ethico-legal perspective to provide the right advice to the customers instead of deploying clever marketing tactics and fineprint to lure customers into debt?

4.1. The Sellers’ Standard of Care

Unlike conventional banks, Islamic banks need to be clearly mindful of the limited scope of credit in Islam, and as suppliers of credit they need to become more customer-centric. They need to educate customers on the true cost of credit and show them the cost-benefit analysis between ‘buy now and pay later’ and ‘save now and buy later’ options. Unfortunately, the current business design of Islamic banks, modeled on conventional banks, is purely product-centric. Given that banks (both Islamic and conventional) make more profit on selling credit products, they often have no incentive to become customer-centric. This is not to say that Islamic banks should not pursue profits. However, unlike conventional banks, Islamic banks should not make profits at the expense of, or to the detriment of, customers. Such a practice would be contrary to Islamic ethico-legal principles. But, one may well wonder, doesn’t the bank always make profit at the expense of the customer in a debt-based product? The answer is no, if banks become customer-centric and educate them about the status of debt in Islam, the true cost of borrowing (like APR) and the cost-benefit analysis between debt and savings, and genuinely offer them saving schemes as alternatives to debt so that customers can “save now and buy later” if they desire. If an Islamic bank provides all the above services and the customer chooses the debt option with full knowledge, then that bank will not be seen as exploiting the customer.

Furthermore, Islamic banks also lack transparency when offering their products. Like conventional product offerings, Islamic banks also often end up showing only the exciting product highlights to capture the customers and artfully obscuring the less exciting and onerous terms under “other terms and conditions apply”, appearing

always as footnotes, and that, too often, in fine print. Although such an offering is legally permissible, given that the Islamic banks set out all the onerous terms in the legal agreement, in reality not many customers actually understand or even read the legalese agreement. Such practice is evidently unacceptable from an Islamic ethico-legal perspective.

The following ethical considerations with regard to sale contracts, as highlighted by al-Zuhayli (2003, pp. 7-8), may shed some light on the scope of the seller's standard of care in Islam:

- i. **The avoidance of excessive profits:** Islam, as well as all other religions, prohibits “excessive profit and taking advantage of buyers”.
- ii. **Truthful and complete disclosure of information:** The seller is required to provide full and truthful information about the product, its type, origin, and cost. Al-Tirmidhī reported a *ḥadīth* on the authority of Rifā‘ah: “All merchants will be resurrected on the Day of Judgment as sinners, except for those who feared Allah, treated their customers well and were truthful.” (as cited in Al-Zuhayli, 2003, p. 7) The buyer's knowledge of the subject matter of the sale contract is considered one of the conditions for the validity of the contract (Al-Zuhayli, 2003, p. 33).
- iii. **Ease of conduct:** Islam also requires both seller and buyer to be reasonable when setting the terms and condition of the contract. Jābir quoted Allah's Messenger (peace be upon him) as saying, “Allah is merciful to the man who is easygoing when he sells, when he buys, and when he collects his loans.” (Al-Bukhari as cited in Al-Zuhayli, 2003, p. 7)
- iv. **Documentation and witnessing of all debts:** All contracts and loans should be written and witnessed as prescribed in the Holy Qur'ān, 2:282.

The discussion above leads us to conclude that Islam calls for justice, fairness, cooperation and shared responsibility in commercial transactions. With regard to debt transactions, Islam imposes a much higher standard of care, as elaborated above. This then implies that debt-based Islamic financial products should not only be Sharī'ah-

compliant or *ḥalāl* but also ‘*ṭayyiban*’ (wholesome, good). What does *ṭayyiban* really mean in the context of debt-based contracts?

Allah SWT mentions at several places in the Qur’ān that He has provided us with sustenance that is ‘*ḥalālan ṭayyiban*’ (i.e. lawful and good). See, for example: 2:168; 5:88; 8:69 and 16:114. These verses imply that the sustenance that Allah SWT has provided for us is not only *ḥalāl* in nature but it is also *ṭayyiban* (wholesome, good) for us. We should apply the same principle to financial instruments; not only should they be Sharī‘ah-compliant (i.e. *ḥalāl*), but they should also be *ṭayyiban* (wholesome, good) in nature. This means that the products should, among other things, be just to both seller (creditor) and buyer (debtor).

In reality, what Islamic banks have done in the past three or more decades is focus all their resources on making their products *ḥalāl* from a purely legal perspective. The Islamic finance industry has, unfortunately, failed to take into consideration the ethico-legal dimensions discussed above. What we have now is comparable to the *ḥalāl* McDonald food chain existing in some Muslim countries. From a purely legal perspective, the Muslim ‘McDonald’ food is *ḥalāl* and may share the same economics in terms of pricing with a non-*ḥalāl* McDonald in the US. But the McDonald food would not become wholesome or healthy merely by being served as *ḥalāl*. What we need, from an ethico-legal perspective is to transform the *ḥalāl* food to become *ṭayyiban*. This ‘wholesome’ food revolution is already happening in the developed world. McDonald is transforming itself to become more customer-centric by disclosing the amount of fat, calories and other contents in its food and giving the consumer the choice between high-calorie fast-food and healthier wholesome food. What we need to see now is a similar transformation in the Islamic finance industry. In other words, we need the Islamic finance industry to evolve from the mere *ḥalāl* stage to the ‘*ḥalālan ṭayyiban*’ stage!

Given that Islamic banks, as suppliers of credit, are subject to a higher standard of care as discussed above, it is only reasonable to impose a similar high standard of care on conventional banks as well. If only Islamic banks are subject to a higher standard, they will become less competitive in the market. It is now incumbent upon Islamic

banks to expand their scope and take the lead to reshape the financial system based on the higher objectives of the Sharī'ah. It is quite evident that Islamic banks will clearly fail in their efforts to reshape the Islamic banking system unless they push for a total reform of the conventional financial system.

Fortunately, the recent global financial crisis has given birth to various initiatives to reform the conventional financial system. Warren and Tyagi (February, 2009) believe that there is a dire need for the establishment of a Consumer Credit Safety Commission (CCSC). This commission would be similar to the Consumer Product Safety Commission (CPSC), which ensures that all the products sold in the USA meet basic safety requirements. The main objective of the CCSC would be to make sure that financial products are more transparent and free from any tricks and traps, which would in turn help consumers to make prudent financial decisions. "Shorter contracts and clearer terms," Warren and Tyagi (p. 22) argue, "could replace lenders' current race to the bottom with a race to the top, based on consumer friendliness and fairness." (See also: Roubini, 2008, p. 44.) Even President Obama showed his support for the establishment of an independent agency that would protect consumers against lending abuses that contributed to the financial crisis (Calmes & Chan, 2010, January 20).

Federal Reserve Chairman Ben S. Bernanke shares the view that consumer protection will bring about financial stability. He says:

Protecting consumers also contributes to financial stability. The increased complexity of many consumer products, as well as their sale by a range of financial institutions to a larger segment of the public, is arguably one of the causes of the current crisis. In the past year or so, the Board has developed extensive new disclosures for a variety of financial products, most notably credit cards, and we are currently in the midst of a major overhaul of mortgage disclosures. Because even the best disclosures are not always adequate, we also comprehensively overhauled our mortgage and credit card regulations to prohibit certain practices (Bernanke, 2009).

One of the steps necessary for strengthening the resilience of Islamic finance, according to the Governor of Bank Negara Malaysia, Dr. Zeti Akhtar Aziz, is the assimilation of Sharī'ah values in the realization of benefits (*maṣālih*) to the relevant

stakeholders. As mentioned above, Islam calls for justice, fairness, cooperation and shared responsibility.

The goals of Islamic finance go far beyond monetary indicators and growth; it promotes ethics and market discipline. Thus, there is a need for “a comprehensive consumer protection framework” (Aziz, 2008; see also OECD, 2009a, p. 10). Protecting consumers is definitely a right thing to do, but it does not mean that the customers themselves have no need to be responsible and active. The general teaching of Islam is that we need to fulfill our commitments and to act with utmost sincerity and responsibility (see the Qur’ān, 5:1; 17:34). As a buyer (borrower), a Muslim is obliged to repay his debts on time and according to the terms agreed with the seller (creditor). Not only that, Islam also encourages him to be gracious and generous when doing so. Once a man came to Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) seeking repayment of his debt. The Prophet instructed an assistant to find a camel of the age that had been borrowed, but the only camel available was one more valuable. Allah’s Messenger (peace be upon him) instructed that it be given to the creditor (Al-Bukhari, 1987/1407b, p. 809).

4.2. The Responsibility of Regulators

Achieving sustainable growth and resilience of the Islamic financial system in particular and the global financial system in general, is a challenging task for the parties involved. Supply (seller) and demand (buyer) sides of the market are but one side of the coin, the other being the regulatory framework together with central banks and governments. In brief, there is a need for an efficient regulatory and supervisory framework that will stay ahead of the market and make sure that the market is not overstretching (Aziz, 2008; Mirakhor & Krichene, 2009).

The proposed consumer protection agency can act as a check-and-balance between the seller (creditor) and buyer (debtor). Obama’s administration proposed that this agency would have power over banks, credit unions and mortgage brokers, and would oversee products including mortgages, credit cards, loan servicing, consumer-reporting data, debt collection and real estate settlements (Calmes & Chan, 2010,

January 20). This way, the agency can follow up on financial development and ensure that there are no abuses in the market.

Furthermore, the regulator must ensure that seller's standards, *caveat venditor*, are imposed on all banks, Islamic or conventional. Otherwise, if these standards are imposed on Islamic banks alone, following the law of one price, there will be 'regulatory arbitrage' and conventional banks will have comparative advantage in the market (at least for a period of time). These standards will make sure that the financial products are not only in line with law, but also in line with ethico-legal considerations.

By complying with ethico-legal requirements, the banks will disclose information and educate their customers about their products. This will lead to greater transparency, responsibility and accountability. Responsibility here refers to educating the customers, while accountability means that the banks will be held accountable if they fail to do so.

One good example related to the above discussion is the Credit Card Accountability Responsibility and Disclosure Act of 2009 (Credit CARD Act 2009). Due to space limitations, we cannot discuss it in detail, but in short, this Act tries to strike a balance between the sellers of credit cards and the buyers. It aims at protecting the latter by imposing some sort of *caveat venditor* standards.

5.0 CONCLUSION

The global financial crisis revealed the weaknesses of the global financial architecture on one side and provided an opportunity for Islamic finance to show its inherent strengths and qualities on the other. Though the current financial crisis has been discussed extensively in the last two years, there is still no clear consensus on the main causes and how to avoid similar financial disasters in the future.

This paper offers some possible Sharī'ah-based solutions that can help the financial world avoid similar crises in the future. In short, there is an urgent need to revamp the

entire financial architecture. All the causes mentioned above result from the inherent flaws and defects in the global financial system, and unless the world takes immediate and wholehearted measures to remedy these flaws, we will inevitably face similar crises in the near future.

These remedial measures are especially important for the Islamic financial industry. As it is still in its infancy stage, the Islamic finance industry has to make sure that it does not repeat the same mistakes made by the conventional financial industry. To avoid them, it needs to change the way it is managing its business, especially when it comes to debt-based products.

On the whole, the global financial crisis provided us with an opportunity to make things better, and the Islamic financial industry should take a leading role in doing so. The paper argues that the industry needs to do two things: One, bearing in mind the limited scope for debt in Islam, it should promote more equity-based products and implement ethico-legal principles when offering debt-oriented products, as discussed above. Second, new standards based on ethico-legal principles should be imposed by regulatory and supervisory bodies on the entire financial services industry, conventional as well as Islamic financial sectors, to ensure that there is no arbitrage between the conventional and Islamic financial sectors.

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International Shari'ah Research Academy for Islamic Finance

International Shari'ah Research Academy for Islamic Finance
ISRA @INCEIF (718736-K)
2nd Floor Annexe Block,
Menara Tun Razak,
Jalan Raja Laut,
50350 Kuala Lumpur,
Malaysia

Tel : +603 2781 4000
Fax : +603 2692 4092
Email : info@isra.my